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Mismatch between STEM Education and Occupation: A Case Study of Thai certificate holders

Sasithorn Supakienmongkol*

*ssupakie@gmu.edu

Schar School of Policy and Government, George Mason University, 3351 Fairfax Dr, Arlington, VA 22201 (United States)

Background

Knowledge, as embodied in human beings as “human capital”, has always been central to economic development (OECD, 1996). Education specifically related to STEM disciplines is vital to long-term economic growth and individual welfare because it stimulates innovation and produces workers able to drive and respond to technological advancement (Atkinson and Mayo 2010). Both U.S. national and local policymakers have long advocated STEM education as a key to American competitiveness (National Academies 2010).

Increases in STEM education benefit the entire world, and it is particularly critical for developing countries. STEM human capital and lifelong learning are important tools for developing countries to escape the middle-income trap. However, most developing countries are now experiencing the STEM shortage challenge. Take Thailand for example, despite notably expanding its educational system, the issue of a STEM human capital shortage still exists. In response to the issue, the Thai government has launched the national policy plan to direct more students into STEM pipeline and to increase the percentage of graduates in STEM fields to be at least 60 percent, an increase by 20 percent from 2011 in which only 40 percent of students enrolled in STEM fields and 60 percent enrolled in social sciences and humanities (UNCTAD 2015).

Throughout the policy to increase human resources in STEM, there was evidence of a STEM education – occupation mismatch in Thai job market. STEM shortage captures a misalignment between supply of and demand for in the labor market. Mismatch, or undersupply of skills on some areas implies that the problems of shortage may have more to do with the issue of mismatches between specific STEM degrees and/or skills sets being sought for specific positions. One of the reasons of the mismatch phenomenon that has always been overlooked is the problem of weak institutions in developing countries. Lack of financial and career incentives for scientists or researchers, low investment on national R&D, few research institute or think tanks, these institutional factors hinder STEM professional opportunities to enter a STEM career and as a result, hold jobs in other fields. These situations may be a sign that the mismatch is not by choice, but because the STEM positions do not exist. The degree of mismatch can also be influenced by individual demographic characteristics such as race and gender. Most studies in this field conclude that STEM workforce is not gender neutral and is largely dominated by

male. Women who major in STEM fields are less likely than their male counterparts to enter STEM occupations or remain in them and earn less salaries. Therefore, individuals who experience gender discrimination are more likely to have STEM education-job mismatch.

Purpose of study

The research agenda focuses on the issue of STEM education-job mismatch – A case study of Thailand. This research aims 1) to examine how the relationships between STEM education and skill mismatches have changed over time, especially after Thailand's government launched national policy plan in 2012; 2) to ascertain whether the notion of Thailand's STEM shortage has more to do with the issue of mismatch between degrees and jobs; 3) to identify specific areas of mismatch; 4) to investigate how the mismatch between job and degree can be influenced by educational outcomes and demographic attributes; 5) to investigate the effect on earnings of working inside and outside one's STEM degree fields.

Significance of study

Little analysis has been performed at identifying the mismatch between STEM graduates and workers shortage in Thailand. To the author's knowledge, this is the first study that examines this relationship. This research will contribute to the current field by highlighting the actors related to degree type, field, geographic location, and demographic characteristics of the STEM degree holders and the influence those factors have upon the worker-job mismatch. A phenomenon of job mismatch brings about the weak coordination among various demand and supply sides stakeholders and poses negative impacts on labor markets due to loss of unused skills, low job satisfaction and productivity, and eventually leads to the waste of the STEM human capital accumulated. It is important for policy makers to understand the issues in order to reshape or formulate the right policy. A better policy recommendation to improve STEM education can be drawn from the consideration of various dimensions in this education-job mismatch study. Furthermore, this research will substantially contribute to the literature of STEM gender disparity and wage discrimination issues.

Methodology and Research Design

Data

The primary data used for this study will result from individual level data from Thailand's National Labor Force Survey (LFS) which is cross-sectional data. The LFS is a quarterly survey conducted by the National Statistical Office of Thailand (NSO), Statistical Forecasting Bureau, Thailand. The 3rd quarter rounds of the survey (July-September) from 2007 to 2016 are utilized. The 3rd quarter round of the LFS is considered the "full employment" round of the survey. The sample used for estimation includes individual full-time workers who work more than 30 hours a week. This study limits the age group of respondents to 21-45 as employees in this group are more likely to be productive and involve in changing career fields.

STEM covers a diverse array of subjects and occupations. This paper defines STEM occupations in two ways. First, the paper follows the traditional U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS) to identify STEM occupations. Under BLS, STEM occupations include computer and mathematical, architecture and engineering, and life and physical science occupations, as well as postsecondary teaching occupations related to these functional areas. Health professionals, health associate professional, managerial and sales occupations are not included in BLS definition. However, STEM tasks are increasingly parts of jobs that are not classified as STEM. By using BLS's definitions of STEM may disadvantage female by excluding STEM-related jobs that are majority women. The paper alternatively follows Speer (2020) in defining STEM

occupations. Speer (2020) uses tasks in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics from the Occupational Information Network (ONET) to create data-driven definitions of STEM occupations. By adding STEM tasks by ONET, medical diagnosing and treating practitioners, as well as medical/health service managers, and all other medical occupations are included.

Workers' occupations in LFS are coded according to the International Standard Classification of Occupations 1988 (ISCO-88). Most of occupations can be defined as STEM occupations by the ISCO code except code "2310 = university and higher education teachers" that does not specify teaching field for teacher. This research assumes that university and higher education teachers are STEM workers if they previously earned a STEM degree.

Table 1. ISCO-08 Occupations list (sub-domain)

Occupations	ISCO 2-digit level
Science and Engineering Professionals	21
Health Professionals	22
Teaching Professionals	23
Information and communications technology professionals	25
Science and Engineering Associate Professionals	31
Health Associate Professionals	32
Information and communication technicians	35

Table 2. ISCED 1997 fields of education

Degree program	ISCED 2-digit level
Teacher training and education science	14
Life sciences	42
Physical sciences	44
Mathematics and statistics	46
Computing	48
Engineering and engineering trades	52
Manufacturing and processing	54
Architecture and building	58
Veterinary	64
Health	72

This research focuses on workers with postsecondary education within this STEM domain. Workers' degrees in LFS are coded according to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED). ISCED codes 14, 42, 44, 46, 48, 52, 54, 58, 64 and 72 are considered STEM.

Method of Analysis

The definition of STEM education-job mismatch is when the skills that a worker possess versus the skills needed for a specific job do not match or there is horizontal mismatch. In order to estimate the mismatch, this study applies a subjective measurement by matching one's educational background with a proper job, referring to criteria developed by U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS) and job description by The International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO). For example, an engineer is required engineering degree, a career in

biochemist, biophysicist must have degree in scientific fields including biochemistry, chemistry, bioengineering, biology etc.

Due to the categorical nature of the outcome variable, the study runs Logistic regression analysis along with descriptive statistics to analyze the factors contributing to STEM education – job mismatch among the respondents. To investigate the return to STEM education, gender wage gap in STEM, and the impacts of mismatch on labor market outcomes, pooled OLS regression approach will be adopted.

Results and Discussion

This research is still in progress. To date, the author has worked with the data from LFS and observed the patterns of mismatches in some STEM degrees especially in engineering across ten- year period. Future work includes improving the matching of educational fields to occupations, adding new analyses that take fuller advantage of the richness of the data set, such as aggregating to the regional level and treating the data as a panel, studying additional forms of discrimination such as age or region, or treating a policy innovation as a break in the series and comparing before and after using a quasi-experimental design.

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